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CONCEPTUAL MODEL – BRIDGING THE MICRO-MACRO CONNECTION FOR ORGANIZATIONAL VALUE CREATION AND PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The paper presents a conceptual paper of a multilevel analysis model in managing human capital for valuable creation and organizational breakthrough performance in the ground of resource-based view and embedded a multilevel model of human capital resources (HCR). Conventionally, the existing literature focusing on a single analysis, either from a macro or micro perspective. Depending on a single level analysis either micro-micro or macro does not describe the research findings thoroughly and could lead to misattribute of theory because analyzing a particular level of study cannot be generalized to all levels. The multilevel human capital resources (HCR) model provides a holistic view rather than focusing on a single analysis, either from a macro or micro perspective. Drawing from this significant reason, this paper used an approach to the conceptualization of the multilevel model to bring the connection of both macro and micro perspectives. The paper serves as an analytical tool with in-depth discussions to extend the existing knowledge of the multilevel model in current literature.

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Introduction

It has been widely acknowledged that effective human management resource (HRM) practices are significant in extracting positive work behaviors among employees (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011) and the recent years show that research attention to the key role of human resource management (HRM) in general and particularly in human capital has raised the importance of resource-based view in gaining competitive advantage as well as the convergence of strategic application (Genc, 2014; Raghavan, 2011; Dunford et al., 2001, Lepak et al., 2006). By linking good HR practice and strategic management to human capital measurement, firms are able to make a number of better-informed decisions that will help to ensure long-term business success (Scarborough & Elias, 2002). This paper will be using a conceptualization of the human capital resource approach proposed by Ployhart & Moliterno (2011), who developed a multilevel model of human capital resource (HCR) by connecting micro, intermediate, and macro levels of scholarship.

The meeting point of this paper is grounded on the theoretical of the resource-based view (RBV) which the first coin by Barney (2000), RBV specified that the firm's unique internal resource arrangement can be a foundation of sustainable competitive advantage. Multilevel examinations in the HR field have helped to show how HR policies motivate individual performance (Lepak et al., 2006), and applying this concept to the HCR will help researchers learn more about how the HCR emerges as well as how its different components work together to efficiently and effectively create a unit-level resource (Nyberg et al., 2012). In addition, leveraging RBV to explore the unit-level human capital resource (HCR) is undergoing a paradigmatic shift with an increased effort to understand human capital as a macro-level construct (Nyberg et al., 2012). This conceptual paper is critically important as the HCR construct need to be specifically analyzed. Indeed, it might not overstate the matter to suggest that the literature does not suggest a common, shared understanding of the unit level HCR construct. Different components of the HCR will have different effects on the formation of the HCR and how it influences unit performance. It is important to take into account the differences that occurred between the components of the HCR and unit performance.

Problem

Furthermore, these differences are likely to behave differently across contexts (Nyberg et al., 2012). In the strategic HRM literature, one current conceptual trend concerns understanding the “black box,” or mechanisms that lead human resource policies and practices to influence unit-level performance. HCR is a valuable unit-level asset that can be a source of competitive advantage. Strategy scholars are increasingly exploring the HCR asset from the “top-down,” trying to understand the organizational processes by which a unit-level HCR is created, and the individual-level human resources it comprises. Conversely, strategic HRM scholars are looking at the HCR from the “bottom-up,” and are trying to understand how HRM policies and practices affect the unit’s HCR. Thus, the current conceptual trends in strategy and the strategic HRM literature suggest that these two bodies of work are converging (Ilmi et al., 2021).

Objectives

Beyond the issues noted above, there is a call for HRM researchers to more explicitly consider sampling issues that are likely to impact the reliability and validity of empirical investigations of the HR system to performance relationships (Lepak et al., 2006). The organization is capable of achieving added value through people and proponents hail it as a revolutionary way of managing people, treating them as assets rather than costs (Baron & Armstrong, 2007). The concept of the multilevel HCR model and its combination to the ground of RBV theory is expected to extend the knowledge in the related existing literature.

Literature review

The conceptual of human capital and human resource management

Some people might get confused about the terms of human resource management (HRM) and human capital (HCM), does the concept of human resource (HR) and human capital (HC) means the same thing or there is a difference between the two, or else it might be two in one classification. This section provides empirical justification on these two terms. Firstly, the definition of both term HRM or HR with HCM or HC is having strong bonds with each other. Human resource management plays a key role in finding and developing the organization’s people as human resources that contribute to and directly affect company success. The term human resource

management (HRM) refers to the design and application of formal systems in an organization to ensure the effective and efficient use of human talent to accomplish organizational goals. This includes activities undertaken to attract, develop, and maintain an effective workforce (Darf & Marcic, 2006). Whereas the human capital defines as an economic value of the knowledge, experience, skills, and capabilities of employees. (Darf & Marcic, 2006).

Human capital is an important element of the intangible assets of an organization. The other intangible assets include copyright, customer relations, brands, and company image. All these, but especially the know-how, imagination, and creativity of employees, areas critical to business success as 'hard' assets. The significance of human assets explains why it is important to measure their value as a means of assessing how well they are used and of indicating what needs to be done to manage them even more effectively (Baron & Armstrong, 2007). To build human capital, HRM develops strategies for finding the best talent, enhancing the talent's skills and knowledge with training programs and opportunities for personal and professional development, and providing compensation and benefits that enhance the sharing of knowledge and appropriately reward people for their contributions to the organization. HR managers create an environment that gives highly talented people compelling reasons to stay with the company (Darf & Marcic, 2006). Mayo (2000) states the essential difference between HCM and HRM is at the former treats people like assets while the latter treats them as costs. However, recent developments in the HRM and the SHRM literature increasingly consider people as an assessment and people expenditures as investments rather than costs. Moreover, SHRM and HCM focus on the importance of adopting an integrated and strategic approach to managing people.

Therefore, the difference between HCM and HRM remains ambiguous. The most recent study (Afioni, 2013) strongly suggests that HCM is under the root of HRM, this study is supported by Walker (2001), the HCM concept is supposed to capture all efforts addressing people issues, not merely to serve as a new name for HRM. It aims to build an understanding that business strategies have people's implications, which require their serious attention, investment, and action. Afioni (2013) argues that HC is not merely a new name for HR. It is the beginning of a new era for HRM, an era where HR is more strategic, more business-oriented, more integrated with other functions, more flexible, and more future-oriented as shown in the proposed HCM framework. One of the fundamental

principles of strategic human resource management (HRM) research is that the impact of human resource (HR) practices on individuals as well as organizations is best understood by examining the bundle, configuration, or system of HR practices in place (Lepak et al., 2006). Therefore, HR and HC are two terms that can't be separated. The concept of HCM complements and strengthens the concept of HRM. It does not replace it. Both HCM and HRM can be regarded as vital components in the process of people management. Each of HRM and HCM also focuses on the importance of adopting an integrated and strategic approach to managing people, which is the concern of all the stakeholders in an organization, not just the people management function.

The concept of HCM reinforce or add to the concept of HRM is by drawing attention to the importance of what Kearns (2005) calls management through measurement, the aim being to establish a clear line of sight between HR interventions and organizational success; strengthens the HRM belief that people are assets rather than costs; focuses attention on the need to base HRM strategies and processes on the requirement to create value through people and thus further the achievement of organizational goals; reinforces the need to be strategic; emphasizes the role of HR specialists as business partners; provides guidance on what to measure and how to measure; underlines the importance of using the measurements to prove that superior people management is delivering superior results and to indicate the direction in which HR strategy needs to go (Armstrong, 2006).

The dimensions of human resource management practices

There is no set of fixed HRM practice dimensions universally accepted by scholars, each scholar may suggest a variety of HRM practices dimensions. This paper proposed four dimensions of HRM practices. The paper has combined recruitment, retention, and career management as one dimension under talent management strategies. Recruitment is the process of finding and engaging the people the organization needs. Selection is that part of the recruitment process concerned with deciding which applicants or candidates should be appointed to jobs (Armstrong, 2014). The concept that the strategic capability of a firm depends on its resource capability in the shape of people (resource-based view) provides the rationale for resourcing strategy. The aim of this strategy is therefore to ensure that a firm achieves competitive advantage by employing more capable people

than its rivals. Robert and John (2008) highlight that recruiting and selecting the people who fit the jobs and who are less likely to leave in the first place, and then orienting them to the company, can greatly increase retention. Organizations also increase employee retention through formal career planning efforts. Employees discuss with their manager's career opportunities within the organization and career development activities that will help the employees grow. Career management consists of the processes of career planning and management succession. Career planning shapes the progression of individuals within an organization in accordance with assessments of organizational needs, defined employee success profiles, and the performance, potential, and preferences of individual members of the enterprise. Management succession planning takes place to ensure that, as far as possible, the organization has the managers it requires to meet future business needs (Armstrong, 2006).

The key to an effective reward system is an understanding of what it is that employees need and expect from the work situation. Traditionally, employers have taken the rational economic man approach, resting on assumptions that labor is exchanged for financial gain, usually in the form of wages or salary. This was an exchange or transactional relationship in which labor was exchanged for payment, a reward extrinsic or independent to the actual work. But money is not the only incentive and modern employment contracts spell out the details not only of wages but other benefits, an important one being job security. While many employees regard wages as essential, they also regard it as equally important that these wages are secured on a regular basis. Moreover, the reward system encourages employees to become motivated (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011; Collings & Wood, 2009).

Performance appraisal is an important technique for developing an effective workforce, which comprises the steps of observing and assessing employee performance, recording the assessment, and providing feedback to the employee (Daft & Marcic, 2006). Well-done performance appraisals can be a source of development information. Performance data on productivity, employee relations, job knowledge, and other relevant dimensions can be gathered in such assessments (Robert & John, 2008).

This dimension involves the enhancement of knowledge, skill, and ability of employees to perform effectively in their job (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011) and to meet employees' expectations that their employers are committed to keeping employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities current (Leventhal, 2006). As organizations compete

and change to increase organizational performance, training of employees and managers becomes even more critical than before. Employees who must adapt to the many changes facing organizations must be trained continually in order to maintain and update their capabilities. Also, managers must have training and development to enhance their managerial and leadership skills and abilities. Consequently, effective training is a crucial component of HR management (Robert & John, 2008).

Scholarly interest in leveraging resource-based theory to explore the unit-level human capital resource (HCR) is undergoing a paradigmatic shift in the strategy with an increased effort to understand HC as a macro-level construct (Nyberg et al., 2012). Human capital theory can be associated with the resource-based view of the firm as developed by Barney (2000). This proposes that sustainable competitive advantage is gained when the firm has a human resource pool that cannot be imitated or substituted by its rivals. It can also be associated with what might be called the competency movement on the grounds that competencies, effectively used, build value in organizations. The assessment of competency levels in performance management processes can reveal trends in the development of a competent workforce and therefore the value of that workforce (Baron & Armstrong, 2007). According to Kostopoulos et al. (2002), the popularity of the resource-based view (RBV) of the firm has turned our focus on the black box of the firm. Theoretically, the central premise of RBV addresses the fundamental question of why firms are different and how firms achieve and sustain competitive advantage by deploying their resources. Clearly, these ideas are not new. During the last 50 years, many management academics have contributed to the development of this topic. Wright et al. (2001) summarized that the RBV has proven to be integral to the conceptual and theoretical development of the strategic HRM, this evolution began when HR researchers recognized that the RBV provided a compelling explanation for why HR practices lead to competitive advantage. The RBV literature suggests that a firm should strive to innovate not only better than competitors but also one step before the competition. By developing dynamic capabilities, for example, a firm is able to adapt to changing industry conditions, learn and exploit new knowledge and articulate an innovative response to previously nonexistent market demand (Kostopoulos et al., 2002).

Sustained competitive advantage is not just a function of single or isolated components, but rather a combination of human capital

elements such as the development of stocks of skills, strategically relevant behaviors, and supporting people management systems. Although there is yet much room for the progress it is fair to say that the theoretical application of the RBV has been successful in stimulating a substantial amount of activity in the SHRM arena. The RBV provides the framework from which HR researchers and practitioners can better understand the challenges of strategy, and thus be better able to play a positive role in the strategic management of firms (Wright et al., 2001).

Another key aspect included in this conceptual model is a competitive advantage which is basically instilled under the RBV theory. This paper emphasized that competitive advantage are two different terms, this is in line with Seidu (2011) who reported that competitive advantage and performance are theoretically distinct and that competitive advantage leads to performance and not the other way round (Newbert, 2007; Newbert, 2008; Powell, 2001). Strategic HRM research (e.g., Takeuchi et al., 2007) grounded in the resource-based view has examined the direct relationship between human capital and performance and not a competitive advantage. Newbert (2008) argued that test the direct relationship between human capital and performance may be incomplete. Consequently, the influence of competitive advantage in the intermediate linkages between human resources (human capital) and organizational performance outcomes (Newbert, 2008; Powell, 2001) are included in the model of this study. Wright et al. (2001) reported that growing acceptance of internal resources as sources of competitive advantage brought legitimacy to HR's assertion that people are strategically important to firm success. HR researchers recognized that the RBV provided a compelling explanation for why HR practices lead to competitive advantage.

Demortier et al. (2014) justified that Ployhart & Moliterno's (2011) recent multilevel model is a major attempt to articulate both perspectives by addressing two nebulous issues. Firstly, is how to explain the creation of a unit-level human capital resource resulting in sustained competitive advantage from the emergence of individuals' knowledge, skills, and abilities. Secondly is how to articulate other individual characteristics, in particular cooperative attitudes and behaviors, with individual human capital in order to explain the creation and accumulation of collective human capital. A firm that has attained a competitive advantage has created more economic value than its competitors. Economic value is generally created by producing products and/or services with either greater benefits at the

same cost compared to competitors or the same benefits at a lower cost compared to competitors (Peteraf & Barney, 2003). From an HRM perspective, a firm that Powell (2001) can exploit its valuable, and rare human resource/capability combinations to effectively attain competitive advantage should be able to improve its performance compared to its competitors (Newbert, 2008).

Rayment (2007) defined spirituality in the workplace as “individuals and organizations seeing work as a spiritual path, as an opportunity to grow and to contribute to society in a meaningful way. It is about care, compassion, and support of others; about integrity and people being true to themselves and others. It means individuals and organizations attempting to live their values more fully in the work they do. According to Srinivasan (2005), organizations that promote a spiritual dimension recognize that employees have both a mind and a spirit, seek to find meaning and purpose in their work, and desire to connect with other employees and be part of a community. Hence Spirituality is an experience that may give employees direction, sense, inner wholeness, provide feelings of thoughtfulness, support, or connectedness. Armstrong (2006) stated that the role of the HR function is to enable the organization to achieve its objectives by taking initiatives and providing guidance and support on all matters relating to its employees. Considering the individual spiritual at work is expected to extend the existing knowledge on how to understand the employees better and how to treat them as real assets to the organization. Mirvis (1997) arisen a question: “What are organizations doing today to help people meet their meaning needs in the workplace?”. Pfeffer (2003) reported that an “important dimension that people value at work is being able to feel part of a larger community or being interconnected”. Garcia-Zamor (2003) stated more than 300 books were published focusing on spirituality in the workplace and up to date, the number is obviously increasing. This has reflected that employees’ spiritual at work is seriously important. Tevichapong (2012) reported that spirituality has been receiving increased attention in organizational sciences and is one of the fastest-growing areas of new research and inquiry by scholars and practitioners alike (e.g., Barrett, 1998; Mitroff & Denton, 1999; Cash & Gray, 2000; Ashmos & Duchon, 2000; Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, 2003; Benefiel, 2003; Fry, 2003; Neal & Biberman, 2003; Giacalone et al., 2005; Kinjerski & Skrypnek, 2004, 2006, 2008; Zaidman et al., 2009).

Dimensions of Individual Spirit at Work There are four dimensions of individual spiritual at work will be used in this study which is

accordingly to the Spirit at Work Scale (SAWS) that developed by Kinjerski & Skrypnek (2006), which consist of four subscales namely engaging work, sense of community, spiritual connection, and mystical experience. Followings are justification of each subscale to according to SAWS:

Engaging work is characterized by a profound feeling of well-being, a belief that one is engaged in meaningful work that has a higher purpose, an awareness of alignment between one's values and beliefs and one's work, and a sense of being authentic.

A sense of community is characterized by a feeling of connectedness to others such as sharing a sense of common purpose, being part of the community at work, and experience a real sense of trust and personal connection with my co-workers.

Spiritual connection identified by a sense of connection to something larger than the self that composed of receive inspiration or guidance and experiences a connection with a greater source that has a positive effect on work as well as individual spiritual beliefs play an important role in everyday decisions at work.

Mystical experience justified as a positive state of energy or vitality, a sense of perfection, transcendence, and experiences of joy and bliss. Job satisfaction from a materialistic or extrinsic perspective is outdated and it is time to move beyond these materialistic factors to more intangible and intrinsic factors (such as spirituality) in order to obtain a better understanding of the meaning of work and how it can influence people's satisfaction level in an organization. An employee with a lower level of job satisfaction will exhibit negative symptoms, such as absenteeism, grievance expression, disloyal and low morale. Employees who derive the most meaning from their work, for example, feel called to their jobs, experience higher job satisfaction (Srinivasan, 2005). HR policies and practices affect job satisfaction (Boxall et al., 2007). The basic requirements for job satisfaction may include comparatively higher pay, an equitable payment system, real opportunities for promotion, considerate and participative management, a reasonable degree of social interaction at work, interesting and varied tasks, and a high degree of autonomy: control over work pace and work methods. The degree of satisfaction obtained by individuals, however, depends largely upon their own needs and expectations, and the working environment (Armstrong, 2006). HR practices and job satisfaction has been extensively studied and it is assumed that HR practices are closely associated with job satisfaction (Ting, 1997). Steijn (2004) also found that HRM

practices had a positive effect on job satisfaction of the employees of the Dutch public sector whereby Gould-William (2003) showed that the use of specific HR practices in local government organizations in the United Kingdom (UK) was associated with a greater degree of job satisfaction as well as a study (Edgar & Geare, 2005) found in New Zealand identified that HRM practices had a significant impact on job satisfaction and perceived organizational.

The proposed conceptual model

Analysis at business level

Firstly, this section provides information on how the study derived the pathway of variables position at business level analysis. In this level of analysis, there are four variables interconnected to each other namely HRM practices, collective of human capital, competitive advantage, and perceived organizational performance as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Variable in business level analysis

Source: Own elaboration

HRM practices, collective human capital, and organizational performance

One of the most notable and earliest study about HRM and performance was conducted by Huselid (1995) who reported that theoretical literature clearly suggests that the behavior of employees within firms has important implications for organizational performance and that human resource management practices can affect individual employee performance through their influence over employees' skills and motivation and through organizational structures that allow employees to improve how their jobs are performed. Daud (2006) asserted that in the 1990s a substantial amount of empirical research carried out to find evidence on the link between HRM practices and performance (e.g. Arthur, 1994; Huselid, 1995; Ichniowski et al., 1997). Consistent result of significant relationship between HRM and organizational performance keep on going to 20th and 21st century

(e.g., Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003; Allen, 2006; Bae & Lawler, 2000; Batt, 2002; Gong et al., 2009; Guthrie, 2001; Wright et al., 2003).

The relationship between human capital and performance

A significant positive relationship has been found between human capital and organizational performance (Alipour et al., 2012; Fleisher et al., 2010). By demonstrating the role of human capital dimensions in their study (Alipour et al., 2012) recommended that top leaders, managers, and HRD departments should focus on human capital in their strategies and policies to improve organizational performance. Crook et al. (2011) presented a meta-analysis counting to 66 studies of the human capital and firm performance relationship confirmed that human capital relates strongly to performance, especially when the human capital is firm-specific, and when operational performance measures are used at the organizational level. However, this meta-analysis study was focusing on firm performance at the business level but not at individual and collective levels of human capital. Demortier et al. (2014) provide more recent empirical evidence of the way that individual HC contributes to building a unit level or collective HC that leverage unit performance. The results (Demortier et al., 2014) show that the relationship between individual and collective human capital is not systematic, but that individual human capital components emerge at the collective level through the moderator effect of collective affective commitment contributes to business unit performance. Secondly, the result demonstrates the positive impact of two HR practices bundles on human capital: at the individual level, leverage individual human capital at the business level. As reported by previous studies from Lepak et al. (2006) and Lepak & Snell (1999) collective human capital has positively related to business unit performance.

Multilevel human capital

Nyberg et al. (2012) asserted that researchers are becoming more interested in exploring the human capital as a mediator between human resource policies and unit performance (Wright et al., 2001; Wright & McMahan, 1992). Several researchers (Newbert, 2008; Powell, 2001) recommended that is a need for research to examine the influence of competitive advantage in the intermediate linkages between human resource (human capital) and organizational performance outcomes. Hence the study will examine the linkage

between HRM, HC, competitive advantage, and organizational performance. Seidu (2011) reported based on the study of the high work performance system (HPWS), the selective staffing and comprehensive training can contribute to a high level of collective human capital for the workforce (e.g., Huselid, 1995; Takeuchi et al., 2007; Zacharatoes et al., 2005). For instance, Guthrie & Olian (1991) showed that selection practices have an effect on the characteristics of employees and managers selected for jobs. Delaney & Huselid (1996) drew attention to the value of HRM practices that emphasize hiring individuals of higher quality, or of raising the level of skills and abilities among the current workforce, or both. Secondly, competitive compensation packages and extensive benefits to employees help to attract and recruit high-caliber individuals (e.g., Arthur, 1994; Guthrie, 2001; Huselid, 1995).

Intermediate linkages of competitive advantage in the hrm and performance

As we can clearly see from the discussion earlier, previous studies performed the analysis either from HRM or HC to performance (Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003; Allen, 2006; Alipour et al., 2012; Arthur, 1994; Bae & Lawler, 2000; Batt, 2002; Crook et al., 2011; Fleisher et al., 2010; Gong et al., 2009; Guthrie, 2001; Huselid, 1995; Ichniowski et al., 1997; Wright et al., 2003). Other more studies in the roof of the resource-based view (e.g., Takeuchi et al., 2007) have examined the direct relationship between human capital and performance, and not including the competitive advantage has been argued to be incomplete set (Newbert, 2008). Previous studies (Barney & Wright, 1998; Boxall, 2003; Pfeffer, 2005; Newbert, 2008) recommended that competitive advantage is a very imperative as accordance with the human resource-based view is by which a firm can improve its performance.

Human capital is a source of a sustained competitive advantage which identified to be potentially valuable, rare, and non-substitutable resource (Ployhart & Moliterno, 2011; Wright et al., 2001), and to reap any performance gains from its human capital resources, organizations must first attain the competitive advantages as an outcome commenced from the effective exploitation of human resources/capabilities. Newbert (2008) found that competitive advantage fully mediated the rare resource/capability- performance relationship. Therefore, based on this argument this study will

examine the association of competitive advantage in the between HRM and organizational performance.

Analysis at individual level

This section is focusing on how each variable namely individual spirit and work and job satisfaction, as well as organizational performance, are interconnected at the individual level of analysis presents by Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variable in individual level analysis

Source: Own elaboration

The relationship between HRM and individual spiritual at work

Rego et al. (2007) found that there was a significant correlation between spirituality at work and self-reported individual performance. The finding suggested that the individuals perceiving a stronger spirituality climate a higher self-report performance level. Milliman (1994) claim spirituality values have positive effects on both personal well-being and job performance. So, Harrington et al. (2001) suggested that the more congruent employees' values and spiritual aspirations are with the organization, the greater the possibility that employees will find true meaning at work. Spirituality and its components must be understood with greater precision to allow businesses to adopt policies and programs that energize the spiritual nature of their employees (Behestifar & Zare, 2013).

Unfortunately, even the HRM plays a key role in finding and developing the organization's people as human resources that contribute to and directly affect company success through effective and efficient use of human talent (Darf & Marcic, 2006) and to create value through people and thus further the achievement of organizational goals (Armstrong, 2006) but there is a very huge gap in research ground focusing on the relationship between HRM practices and individual spiritual at work. The concept of spirituality in the workplace has increasingly gained popularity in the past few years (Behestifar & Zare, 2013) but it is still limited under HRM studies. Much of the previous study connecting spiritual at work with

stress (Atkins, 2007; Bell et al., 2012), turnover intention (Jamal, 2007), and organizational citizenship in accordance with recent meta-analysis (Dalal, 2005). Hence, in this study, the role of individual spirit at work as moderator will be examined in the relationship between HRM practices and job satisfaction.

Individual spiritual at work with job satisfaction and individual performance

There is growing evidence shows a positive relationship between individual spirituality at work and job satisfaction by previous studies (Chawla & Guda, 2010; Wrzesniewski, 2003; Brown, 1992; Milliman et al., 2003, Reave, 2005, Srinivasan, 2005). According to Srinivasan (2005) job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is one among the foremost used variables in Organizational Behavior and it is an employee's attitudinal response to his or her organization. It is an important key variable that indicates the degree to which individuals like their jobs and which impacts the performance of an organization.

Figure 3: Summary of conceptual multilevel model of human capital resources

Source: Own elaboration

Marschke et al. (2009) reported that the results of their research are congruent with other studies of spirituality in the workplace (Rego, 2007, Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, 2003, Moore & Casper, 2006; Kolodinsky et al., 2007) suggesting that when people find meaning in

their work activities and feel involved in a spiritual organizational climate, they become happier and healthy employees engaged in a collaborative manner, to apply the full potential to work and bring their entire selves to the organization. The strength of the relationship between HRM and performance is stronger or even only exists in certain circumstances, which are uncommon. Nevertheless, Delery & Doty (1996) study is a rare exception who examine the intermediate variables between HRM and performance, the study of Delery & Doty (1996) have found that job satisfaction has mediated the relationship between HRM and performance. Numerous scholars and practitioners believe that sound HR practices result in a better level of job satisfaction which ultimately improves organizational performance (Appelbaum et al., 2000; Zainurossalamia et al., 2020). Figure 3 combined the business and individual level analysis becomes a multilevel model of human capital resources that presents a conceptual distinction, which captures the bridging point between micro and macro analysis. From the assessment of HRM practices, the analysis breakdown into management perspective (Business level) and employees' perspective (individual level), and the connecting point between them is at the perceived organizational performance. A consistent result between these two levels is desirable and leads to a strong justification for consistent results. However, if these two levels are presenting contrasting outcomes, it will call the comparative reviews between the two and stem the temptation to seek a solution or identify the problematic zones.

Conclusion

This paper offers a conceptual framework of how individual and business levels are combined as a multilevel human capital resource by accentuating the HRM practices into organizational performance. At an individual level, potential independent variables of individual spirituality at work and job satisfaction included. At the business level, collective human capital incorporated at the proposed model and that would lead to competitive advantage and then perceived organizational performance. The proposed conceptual model in this study bridging the points between micro and macro analysis, and that is expected to reap the full advantages of multilevel HCR. The application of the emerging multilevel paradigm of the HCR model proposed in this paper will provide an understanding and guideline for future research undertaking in a multilevel of HRM studies.

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